

THERMALLY ACTIVATED HEALING IN HIGH PERFORMANCE CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

K. Pingkarawat¹, C. Dell'Olio², R.J. Varley² and A.P. Mouritz¹

¹Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University, GPO Box 2476, Melbourne, Victoria 3001, Australia.

Email: khomkrit.pingkarawat@rmit.edu.au

²CSIRO Manufacturing Flagship, Private Bag 33, Clayton South MDC, Victoria 3169, Australia.

Email: russell.varley@csiro.au

Keywords: (Poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid); Polymers; Self-healing; Polymer matrix composites (PMCs); Fracture toughness

ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the use of poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) as a healing agent in high performance carbon fibre epoxy composites by exploring different curing regimes that contain steps that are above and below the melting point of EMAA ($T_{m,EMAA}$). The healing performance of EMAA when the composite was cured via a two-stage process (cure below $T_{m,EMAA}$ followed by above $T_{m,EMAA}$) and a single-stage process (cure above $T_{m,EMAA}$ only) was compared and assessed. The healing efficiency of EMAA in high temperature cure epoxy resins was also evaluated using diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) or tetraglycidyl diamino diphenyl methane (TGDDM) as the epoxy resin with two aromatic amine hardeners, namely diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA) and diamino diphenyl sulphone (44 DDS). The healing efficiency was evaluated at three healing temperatures relative to the glass transition temperature of the mendable composites (T_g) comprising below T_g , at T_g or above T_g and followed up to five healing cycles. It was found that EMAA showed excellent healing of delamination cracks when cured according to the two-step cured and with DETDA as hardener but displayed very poor healing when cured in the one step cure or using 44 DDS as a hardener. Healing below T_g , at T_g or above T_g for the two-step cure DGEBA/DETDA resulted in partial, fully recovery and more than fully recovery of the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the mendable composite, respectively, and these recoveries were maintained throughout five healing cycles. However, only healing above T_g for the two-step cure TGDDM/DETDA that showed full recovery, while healing at T_g or below T_g showed partial recovery in fracture toughness and these recoveries continuously decrease throughout five healing cycles. Fractographic analysis confirmed the pressure delivery mechanism occurred at the EMAA-epoxy interface and the importance of the initial low-temperature cure stage. The study also reveals the importance of curing at low enough temperature to ensure solid state surface reactions that ultimately maintain the well known pressure delivery mechanism when the cure temperature is raised above the melting point of the EMAA.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intrinsic self-healing polymer composites can be created either by incorporating reversible functional groups directly into a polymer structure or using a modifier with inherently reversible behavior [1-4]. Subject to some external stimuli, the reversible chemical or physical process becomes activated thereby reducing or eliminating damage. These so called mendable resins have several advantages over more highly engineered alternatives, most notably their simplicity, repeatability and dormancy. Mendable resins using additives with inherently reversible behavior, such as polymers that exhibit large viscosity changes with temperature [5-8], miscible thermoplastics that migrate through nano-space [9, 10], thermosetting/thermoplastic polymer matrices with controlled microstructures [11] and shape memory alloys [12] are also being actively investigated. Intrinsic healing therefore is an attractive self-healing technology contributing solutions to the challenge of service life extension and reparability for materials and components [13].

This study continues to develop the thermoplastic modifier poly(ethylene-*co*-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) as a healing agent in brittle epoxy polymer composites to create new high performance mendable resins. First discovered by Meure et al [14, 15], EMAA has been shown to be highly effective as an immiscible additive using reactive room temperature cure resins and composites based upon diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) and triethylene tetramine (TETA). Studies have demonstrated that EMAA based healing is robust and efficient when used as particles [5, 14, 16-18], as fibres with varying diameter in a woven or non-woven fabric [14, 16, 17, 19, 20], as through thickness stitches with different densities and diameters [6, 21-24] and finally as a blend with other epoxy resins [25]. Indeed, healing has consistently exhibited well over 100% recovery of fracture toughness, irrespective of form or composition when compared with the virgin polymer network or composite. The healing mechanism has been shown to derive from a condensation reaction between hydroxyl groups from the epoxy/amine network formed during cure or post-cure and the carboxylic acid groups of EMAA. This reaction however, is dependent upon tertiary amine catalysis during the later stages of cure, emphasizing the importance of the reaction mechanism, final conversion and reactivity in determining healing [26]. The water produced at the thermoplastic-epoxy interface coalesces into a bubble that embeds within the EMAA thermoplastic and remains dormant until activated by heat [27]. When healing is activated at 150 °C, well above the melting point of the EMAA, the bubble expands greatly, pushing the molten thermoplastic into any cavity or damaged region to bind the fracture surfaces together. While EMAA has been shown to be a highly effective healing agent for the room temperature cure resin system, DGEBA/TETA, the low melting point of EMAA ($T_{m, EMAA}$) of 85 °C has limited the range of epoxy/amine resins evaluated because of the perceived need to ensure that EMAA remains solid and immiscible during the entire cure of the epoxy resin. To develop this technology further therefore, it is important to be able to apply it to a much wider range of epoxy resins, such as those suitable for more demanding, structural or high temperature applications.

In this paper, EMAA modified and unmodified epoxy resins were cured separately with two aromatic amine hardeners. An initial curing step curing below $T_{m, EMAA}$ was added to an otherwise single isothermal cure profile curing above $T_{m, EMAA}$ and compared against a simple isothermal cure above $T_{m, EMAA}$. Healing temperature, efficiency and repeatability and mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the EMAA modified composites was explored using dual cantilever beam testing (DCB) while the mechanism was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and near infra-red (NIR) spectroscopy. Prior to fabricating the fibre reinforced composites, rheological behavior during cure of the resin was determined to understand the changes in viscosity of the matrix. Thermal analysis such as dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) of the cured neat resin systems was performed to make informed decisions on appropriate healing temperatures with respect to the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured network.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Two types of epoxy resin were used including, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) or tetraglycidyl diamino diphenyl methane (TGDDM). The aromatic amines diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA) and 44 diamino diphenyl sulphone (44 DDS) were used. The poly(ethylene-*co*-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) were used in particles form (295-495 μm). The plain weave carbon fibre consisted of a 3K tows with a 200 g/m^2 areal density. The chemical structures are shown in Figure 1.

The neat resin DGEBA/DETDA and TGDDM/DETDA formulations were prepared by heating the DGEBA and TGDDM to about 50-70 °C then adding the DETDA liquid amine to both epoxies using a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio. Each resin types were then poured into silicon moulds and cured in an oven according to two different cure profiles (Table 1). The neat resin DGEBA/44 DDS and TGDDM/44 DDS formulation were prepared by adding the 44 DDS to the DGEBA or TGDDM at room temperature using a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio, followed by heating to 130 °C. Then, 1.5wt% of BF_3

catalyst was blended into the resin in which was poured into silicon moulds and cured using the 2 step cure profile only (Table 1).

Unmodified and 10 wt% EMAA modified DGEBA/DETDA, TGDDM/DETDA, DGEBA/44 DDS and TGDDM/44 DDS carbon fibre reinforced composites were fabricated according to the cure profiles shown in Table 1. For the unmodified composites, the resins were prepared in the same manner as described above. The composites were fabricated using a [0]₂₄ ply sequence. In the case of the EMAA modified composites, the DGEBA or TGDDM resins were heated to 65 °C then the EMAA particles were added and evenly dispersed thoroughly. The amine, either the DETDA or the 44 DDS was then blended or dissolved as described above. The resin containing 10 wt% EMAA was however, only applied to the central 5 layers of the composite. The layup stack was then vacuum bagged and cured using a platen press with a one and two step cure profiles described in Table 1.

2.2 Thermal Analysis

DSC was performed to determine the T_g of the cured neat resin epoxy polymer networks and $T_{m,EMAA}$. Samples were heated from 30°C to 300°C and 30°C to 200°C in the epoxy network and EMAA, respectively, at a rate of 10 °C/min. DMTA was performed to determine the T_g of the cured resin and composite. Samples were placed in the dual cantilever mode and heated from 50 °C to 300 °C at a rate of 2 °C/min while applying a 20 µm deformation via the central drive shaft at a frequency of 1 Hz. The samples were approximately 50 mm long x 10 mm wide x 0.5-2 mm thick. Changes in the complex viscosity of the resin during polymerisation were measured using a rheometer. Uncured resin samples were placed between 20 mm diameter parallel plates with a gap of 0.5 mm and pre-heated to the initial temperature of 50 °C and then heated according to the 1 and 2 step cure profiles described in Table 1. Measurements were made at a frequency of 1 Hz until the resin had achieved gelation.

2.3 Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness and self-healing efficiency of the composites were assessed using the double cantilever beam (DCB) test in close accordance with ASTM D5528-01 specifications. The DCB specimens were 170 mm long and 20 mm wide with a 50 µm non-adhesive crack starter film into the mid-plane of the composite. The pre-cracked end of the specimens was loaded in tension at a crack opening displacement rate of 2 mm/min. The delamination crack was grown along the specimen mid-plane in short increments (of approximately 2 to 10 mm). At each increment the applied load (P), crack opening displacement (δ) and crack length (a) values were measured. Using this data, the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was calculated using:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta l|)} \quad (1)$$

where b is the width of the DCB specimen. $|\Delta l|$ is a correction factor to account for vertical displacement and rotation effects at the delamination crack tip, and it was determined from the change in the specimen compliance with increasing crack length.

After DCB testing, the delamination was healed by heating temperatures given in Table 2. Each healing condition was conducted for 30 minutes with a light pressure of 20 kPa applied to close the delamination. The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the DCB specimens was then re-measured according to the test conditions described above. The healing efficiency (η) was determined by the percentage recovery in fracture toughness:

$$\eta = \frac{G_{Ic}(\text{healed})}{G_{Ic}(\text{original})} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

where G_{Ic} (healed) and G_{Ic} (original) are the steady-state mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite after healing and in the original condition, respectively. To explore the ability to assess the repeatability of healing, the method was applied five times.

2.4 Microstructure Analysis

Near infra-red spectroscopy (NIR) spectra of the neat cure resin systems were collected using a Spectrometer FTIR in transmission mode. Samples of approximately 2 mm thickness were placed in the beam and measurements were made in the range of 4000-7500 cm^{-1} taking an average of 32 scans. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on the samples was conducted by initially coating the samples with iridium coated with a thickness of approximately 200 Å using a sputter coater. Once coated, the samples were placed into a Field Emission Scanning Electron microscope (FESEM) for imaging. An accelerating voltage of 5kV was used for the images.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Controlling Epoxy Network Structure

While the condensation reaction is critical to the effectiveness of the pressure delivery healing mechanism, it is actually just the final necessary reaction in a sequence of chemical reactions shown in Figure 2. At low temperature, the epoxy resin and amine hardener attach to the EMAA surface via hydrogen bonding and ionic associations, respectively, as shown Figure 2a and b. At higher cure temperatures, two competing reactions can then take place with the EMAA carboxylic acid groups, either epoxide reaction (Figure 2c) or hydroxyl (condensation) reaction (Figure 2d). The epoxide reaction is likely to occur first during the early stages of cure, given the lower concentration of hydroxyl and tertiary amine groups and high concentration of epoxide groups. However, the hydroxyl reaction increasingly dominates at later stages of cure as the concentration of hydroxyl and tertiary amine groups increase. Both reactions no doubt promote adhesion of the EMAA to the cured epoxy matrix, but it is this condensation reaction that ultimately produces the water bubble within the EMAA that determines the effectiveness of the pressure delivery mechanism. It is the comparative importance of these individual reactions that is investigated in this work.

Rheological analysis was first used to explore the changes in the viscosity of the polymer network by mimicking the fabrication conditions of the EMAA modified epoxy composites. The changes in viscosity for the one- and two-step cure of DGEBA/DETDA and TGDDM/DETDA are shown in Figure 3. As expected, the one-step cure of DGEBA/DETDA and TGDDM/DETDA greatly reduces the time to gelation (and presumably vitrification) compared with the extended two-step cure profile, but more importantly likely affects the sequence of the reactions described above, either by inhibiting non-covalent binding or greatly favoring the epoxide reaction with EMAA carboxylic acid groups at the expense of the condensation reaction. The additional low temperature cure step (below $T_{m,EMAA}$) in the two-step cure, produces a modest but consistent increase in viscosity without any gelation of the network, but when the curing temperature is increased to above $T_{m,EMAA}$, the viscosity reduces sharply, then increases rapidly as crosslinking followed by gelation takes place. Rheological analysis of the DGEBA/44 DDS resin system, designed for similar reactivity through the judicious use of Lewis acid BF_3 catalyst, displayed similar behavior to the DGEBA/DETDA but at a higher viscosity. As for the two-step cured TGDDM/44 DDS resin system catalysed with BF_3 , this resin system displayed intermediate behavior with a period of time, albeit much less than the corresponding TGDDM/DETDA resin system, at relatively low viscosity prior to gelation time. Rheological analysis of the viscosity changes observed during this two-step cure for these resin systems appeared to be more conducive to the sequential occurrence of the reactions described above and thus healing. It is also suggested that the gradually increasing viscosity during this pre-cure step, may also help to protect the EMAA from degradation by a crude type of reversible encapsulation.

Results of the thermal analysis of the cured networks and EMAA are shown in Table 3. Note the low melting point of the EMAA at 85 °C compared with the high T_g of the cured epoxy networks depending upon the type, composition, cure profile and technique of measurement. The T_g s for the DGEBA/DETDA one- and two-step cure profiles are comparatively quite similar at 169 °C and 171 °C, respectively. The T_g s for the TGDDM/DETDA one- and two-step cure profiles are also quite

similar at 236 °C and 218 °C, respectively. These T_g s were obtained by measuring at the maximum the $\tan \delta$ spectra. The T_g of the DGEBA/44 DDS and TGDDM/44 DDS cured resins, however produced a higher T_g than the DGEBA/DETDA and TGDDM/DETDA, respectively, due to the increased thermal stability of the sulphone groups within the 44 DDS.

The healing temperatures shown in Table 3 used were chosen based upon the results of these spectra to explore the role of molecular mobility in controlling healing. At a healing temperature below T_g of the epoxy networks (Table 3), the epoxies are glassy and thus mobility is severely limited by diffusional factors. Healing at this temperature would thus very clearly reflect the mobility and adhesion of EMAA within a rigid polymer network. At a healing temperature above T_g of the epoxy networks (Table 2), the epoxies are in rubbery stages, having enhanced molecular mobility and more able to promote adhesion to the matrix, a particularly beneficial aspect to healing. Healing temperature at T_g therefore, represents intermediate behavior as the storage modulus is just beginning to decrease. Each of these healing temperatures therefore provide important insights into the effectiveness of the healing mechanism for different physical states of the epoxy matrix.

These neat resin results however, do not take into account the impact that EMAA may have upon the T_g of final epoxy networks, so to confirm the relevance of these healing temperatures within EMAA modified composites, the central layers of the laminates, where the EMAA was placed, were removed and characterized using DMTA. The results showed a reduction in T_g of between 6 °C and 17 °C. Hence, this slight reduction in T_g does not impact the validity of the choice of healing temperatures.

3.2 Healing

The low temperature cure step (i.e. below $T_{m,EMAA}$) was used to determine whether or not promoting non-covalent interactions between the epoxy network and solid EMAA phase would enable healing. Figure 4a shows that this indeed was the case as the two-step cure DGEBA/DETDA composite displays almost full recovery in mode I interlaminar fracture toughness during healing at T_g and greater than full recovery at above T_g . The two-step cure TGDDM/DETDA composite, however, showed partial and full recovery in fracture toughness when healed at T_g and above T_g , respectively (Figure 4b). In contrast, the one-step cure composites exhibit absolutely no healing at all regardless of healing temperature. The DGEBA/44 DDS and TGDDM/44 DDS composites were also cured using the two-step cure profile, but displayed only very modest healing, suggesting that amine reactivity plays an important role in determining healing efficiency. These results therefore represent the first successful development of a high performance EMAA modified mendable resin system using DGEBA/DETDA or TGDDM/DETDA in a carbon fibre composite.

The healing mechanism was investigated using SEM to examine the fracture surfaces of the EMAA modified systems. Representative images shown in Figure 5 and 6 after healing at T_g and above T_g illustrate very different behavior between the one- and two-step cure DGEBA/DETDA composites. Note that the fracture surfaces of the one- and two-step cure TGDDM/DETDA mendable composites have the same morphology as the DGEBA/DETDA system. The fracture surfaces of the one-step cure profile exhibit a smooth molten morphology (Figure 5a and 6a). There is obviously no pressure delivery mechanism operating as the EMAA appears to have simply melted and flowed around the fracture surfaces. In contrast, the fracture surfaces of the two-step cured composites (Figure 5b and 6b) display a plethora of bubbles and cavities of all shapes and sizes, ranging from less than 2 μm in diameter to more than 20 μm . The presence of bubbles and ductile tearing of the EMAA on the surface strongly reflects the operation of the pressure delivery mechanism. It is proposed that the one-step cure profile inhibits the EMAA carboxylic acid and hydroxyl reaction (Figure 2d) later in the cure by greatly favoring the EMAA carboxylic acid epoxide reaction (Figure 2c) throughout the cure. Despite the formation of hydroxyl groups later in the cure, the condensation reaction is inhibited due to the unavailability of EMAA carboxylic acid groups as they are consumed via reaction with the epoxy resin. In contrast for the two-step cure, it is proposed that non-covalent attachment of the epoxide and amino functional groups to the EMAA (Figure 2a) effectively shields the EMAA

carboxylic acid groups during the early stages of elevated cure, which enables the condensation reaction later in the cure as the non-covalent attachments dissociate to free up the EMAA carboxylic acid groups for reaction.

In addition, the corresponding fracture surfaces of the two-step cure DGEBA/44 DDS mendable composite, in Figure 5c and 6c shows different behaviour. At a healing temperature at T_g there is certainly little if any evidence of the pressure delivery mechanism, although healing above T_g more bubbles are apparent on the fracture surface and there remains evidence of matrix ductility. While this might be responsible for the small amount of healing observed, overall it appears that the extent of pressure delivery mechanism operating is very modest. Note that the fracture surface morphology of the TGDDM/44DDS mendable composite was similar to the DGEBA/44 DDS system. To understand why mendable composite with 44 DDS does not produce healing comparable with the mendable composite with DETDA despite using the two-step cure profile, NIR spectroscopy was used to investigate the cured unmodified network structures. The NIR spectra for the unmodified resins are shown in Figure 7 **Error! Reference source not found.** and attention is drawn to the secondary amine peaks at 6600 cm^{-1} . The one- and two-step cure resin system with DETDA both have very small secondary amine peaks compared to the resin system with 44 DDS which has a very strong secondary amine peak. This indicates higher secondary amine cure conversion (i.e. tertiary amine formation) for the DETDA resins compared with less tertiary amine formation for the 44 DDS cured network. This can be attributed to the electron withdrawing effect of the sulphone group deactivating the 44 DDS and the mildly activating effect of the electron donating ethyl groups of the DETDA. Higher secondary amine conversion in the DETDA networks directly impacts the concentration of tertiary amine groups which are catalysts for the condensation reaction at the interface between the carboxylic acid groups in EMAA and hydroxyl groups in epoxy resin. NIR shows clearly therefore that the deactivating nature of 44 DDS reduces tertiary amine concentration and ultimately reducing healing.

As healing was only achieved for the two-step EMAA modified DGEBA/DETDA or TGDDM/DETDA composites, repeatability was only explored for these two systems. Figure 8 shows the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness recovery of the corresponding composites as a function of healing event for three different healing temperatures used (i.e. below T_g , at T_g and above T_g). For the EMAA modified DGEBA/DETDA composites, the results showed excellent levels of repeatability, particularly healing below T_g and at T_g which exhibit little if any decrease in healing efficiency as a function of damage event. Even healing above T_g , although there is a gradual decrease in healing efficiency, it remains above 70% healing even after the 5th healing event. Healing increases with healing temperature presumably due to an increase in chemical reactions at the EMAA particle-matrix interface, the reduced viscosity of the EMAA and the softer nature of the epoxy network. These factors aid healing from more efficient bubble formation within the thermoplastic and better viscous flow of the EMAA. While the extent of healing is much lower when healing below T_g , being about 50%, the epoxy matrix remained completely in the glassy state and represents an excellent example of healing agent mobility and adhesion whilst remaining in a rigid cross-linked network. As for the two-step cure EMAA modified TGDDM/DETDA composite, the results show that healing was indeed repeatable up to 5 healing cycles, but tended to decreased more rapidly than the DGEBA/DETDA mendable composites. This was particularly the case when healed above T_g which decreased from about 110% healing efficiency after the 1st heal event, down to less than 10% efficiency after the 5th healing event. The large decrease for multiple healing events when healed above T_g is likely a result of increased degradation arising from thermal cycling. Although repeatability reduces consistently with healing events, healing efficiency remains higher at higher healing temperatures, except for the 4th and 5th healing events, indicative of the importance of chemical reactions at the EMAA particle-matrix interface, the reduced viscosity of the EMAA and the softer nature of the epoxy network. SEM explored the robustness of the healing mechanism after multiple healing events by examining the fracture surfaces of the repeatedly healed samples and shown that they appear relatively similar to the fracture surface of the 1st healing cycle regardless of healing temperature (Figure 5 and 6), indicative of a robust healing mechanism, as already exhibited by the consistency of the healing efficiencies achieved. Some differences observed on the fracture surfaces after repeated healing however are the

presence of porous structure with smaller but more plentiful cavities. This possibly reflects a reduced capacity to produce more bubbles from the pressure delivery mechanism and a collapsing of bubbles with increased healing cycles. This would explain the very modest reduction in healing efficiencies observed.

4. CONCLUSION

The use of EMAA ($T_{m,EMAA}$ of 85 °C) as an efficient and repeatable healing agent in a high performance mendable DGEBA/DETDA and TGDDM/DETDA composites has been successfully demonstrated for the first time. The key to this development was the design of an appropriate cure profile that included a low temperature cure step below $T_{m,EMAA}$ prior to cure above $T_{m,EMAA}$. During this additional cure step, non-covalent hydrogen bonding and ionic associations bind the epoxy resin and amine to the EMAA surface facilitating interfacial condensation reactions at higher cure temperature by shielding the EMAA carboxylic acid groups from epoxide reaction, despite being well above $T_{m,EMAA}$. Amine reactivity was also found to greatly impact healing, with the more reactive DETDA exhibiting excellent healing compared with the slower 44 DDS displaying very low healing. This was attributed to the increased formation of tertiary amine for DETDA compared with 44 DDS, which correlated directly with the ability to catalyse the condensation reaction and hence healing. Varying the healing temperature from below to above the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the epoxy network showed that higher levels of healing were achieved at higher temperature due to the combination of increased pressure buildup within the water bubble, lower EMAA viscosity and enhanced molecular mobility and adhesiveness of the epoxy network. Importantly, about 40-50% healing was still achieved during healing below T_g despite the epoxy network being in its glassy state.

5. REFERENCES

1. S.D. Bergman and F. Wudl, *Mendable polymers*. Journal of Materials Chemistry, 2008. **18**(1): p. 41-62.
2. Y.C. Yuan, T. Yin, M.Z. Rong, and M.Q. Zhang, *Self healing in polymers and polymer composites. Concepts, realization and outlook: A review*. Express Polymer Letters, 2008. **2**(4): p. 238-250.
3. S. van der Zwaag, *Routes and mechanisms towards self healing behaviour in engineering materials*. Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences-Technical Sciences. **58**(2): p. 227-236.
4. B.J. Blaiszik, S.L.B. Kramer, S.C. Olugebefola, J.S. Moore, N.R. Sottos, and S.R. White, *Self-Healing Polymers and Composites*, in *Annual Review of Materials Research, Vol 40*, D.R. Clarke, M. Ruhle, and F. Zok, Editors. 2010. p. 179-211.
5. K. Pingkarawat, T. Bhat, D.A. Craze, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Healing of carbon fibre-epoxy composites using thermoplastic additives*. Polymer Chemistry, 2013. **4**(18): p. 5007-5015.
6. T. Yang, C.H. Wang, J. Zhang, S. He, and A.P. Mouritz, *Toughening and self-healing of epoxy matrix laminates using mendable polymer stitching*. Composites Science and Technology, 2012. **72**(12): p. 1396-1401.
7. M. Zako and N. Takano, *Intelligent material systems using epoxy particles to repair microcracks and delamination damage in GFRP*. Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures, 1999. **10**(10): p. 836-841.
8. M. Zako, N. Takano, and H. Fujioka. *Intelligent materials system using Epoxy particles for self-repair*. in *8th Eighth Japan/US Conference on Composite Materials*. 1998. Baltimore, Md: Taylor and Francis.
9. S.A. Hayes, W. Zhang, M. Branthwaite, and F.R. Jones, *Self-healing of damage in fibre-reinforced polymer-matrix composites*. Journal of the Royal Society Interface, 2007. **4**(13): p. 381-387.
10. S.A. Hayes, F.R. Jones, K. Marshiya, and W. Zhang, *A self-healing thermosetting composite material*. Composites - Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2007. **38**: p. 1116-1120.

11. X.F. Luo, R.Q. Ou, D.E. Eberly, A. Singhal, W. Viratyaporn, and P.T. Mather, *A Thermoplastic/Thermoset Blend Exhibiting Thermal Mending and Reversible Adhesion*. ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces, 2009. **1**(3): p. 612-620.
12. J. Nji and G. Li, *A biomimic shape memory polymer based self-healing particulate composite*. Polymer. **51**(25): p. 6021-6029.
13. S. van der Zwaag, ed. *Self Healing Materials: An Alternative Approach to 20 Centuries of Materials Science*. ed. S.v. Zwaag. Vol. 1. 2007, Springer: Dordrecht. 388.
14. S. Meure, S. Furman, and S. Khor, *Poly[ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid)] Healing Agents for Mendable Carbon Fiber Laminates*. Macromolecular Materials and Engineering, 2010. **295**(5): p. 420-424.
15. S. Meure, D.Y. Wu, and S. Furman, *Polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid healing agents for mendable epoxy resins*. Acta Materialia, 2009. **57**(14): p. 4312-4320.
16. K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Self-healing of delamination cracks in mendable epoxy matrix laminates using poly ethylene-co-(methacrylic acid) thermoplastic*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2012. **43**(8): p. 1301-1307.
17. K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Self-healing of delamination fatigue cracks in carbon fibre-epoxy laminate using mendable thermoplastic*. Journal of Materials Science, 2012. **47**(10): p. 4449-4456.
18. K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Mechanical properties of mendable composites containing self-healing thermoplastic agents*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2014. **65**(0): p. 10-18.
19. K. Hargou, K. Pingkarawat, A.P. Mouritz, and C.H. Wang, *Ultrasonic activation of mendable polymer for self-healing carbon-epoxy laminates*. Composites Part B: Engineering, 2013. **45**(1): p. 1031-1039.
20. R.J. Varley and G.P. Parn, *Thermally activated healing in a mendable resin using a non woven EMAA fabric*. Composites Science and Technology, 2012. **72**(3): p. 453-460.
21. K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Healing of fatigue delamination cracks in carbon-epoxy composite using mendable polymer stitching*. Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures, 2014. **25**(1): p. 75-86.
22. T. Yang, J. Zhang, A.P. Mouritz, and C.H. Wang, *Healing of carbon fibre-epoxy composite T-joints using mendable polymer fibre stitching*. Composites Part B-Engineering, 2013. **45**(1): p. 1499-1507.
23. K. Pingkarawat, C.H. Wang, R.J. Varley, and A.P. Mouritz, *Effect of mendable polymer stitch density on the toughening and healing of delamination cracks in carbon-epoxy laminates*. Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2013. **50**: p. 22-30.
24. K. Pingkarawat and A.P. Mouritz, *Stitched mendable composites: Balancing healing performance against mechanical performance*. Composite Structures, 2015. **123**(0): p. 54-64.
25. M. Dell'Olio, Q. Yuan, and R. Varley, *Epoxy/Poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) Blends as Thermoplastic Healing Agents in an Epoxy/Amine network*. Macromolecular Materials and Engineering, 2014. **in press**.
26. S. Meure, D.Y. Wu, and S.A. Furman, *FTIR study of bonding between a thermoplastic healing agent and a mendable epoxy resin*. Vibrational Spectroscopy, 2010. **52**(1): p. 10-15.
27. S. Meure, R.J. Varley, D.Y. Wu, S. Mayo, K. Nairn, and S. Furman, *Confirmation of the healing mechanism in a mendable EMAA-epoxy resin*. European Polymer Journal, 2012. **48**(3): p. 524-531.

Figure 1 Chemical structures of a) diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A ($n=0.17$), b) tetraglycidyl methylene dianiline (TGDDM), c) diethyl toluene diamine (DETDA), d) 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (44DDS) and e) poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA)

Figure 2. Chemical interactions providing the source of the pressure delivery healing mechanism. The 1st cure step at below $T_{m,EMAA}$ involves non-covalent chemical interactions between the surface carboxylic acid groups of the EMAA, and a) hydrogen bonding and b) ionic associations. The 2nd cure step above $T_{m,EMAA}$ involves covalent chemical reactions between the absorbed c) epoxide groups of d) hydroxyl groups catalysed by tertiary amine from the absorbed epoxy resin and amine.

Figure 3. a) viscosity plots showing the curing behaviour of the (a) DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44DDS resin when subjected to a one- and a two-step cure and (b) TGDDM/DETDA and TGDDM/44DDS resin when subjected to a one- and a two-step cure.

Figure 4. Extent of property restoration of the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness for the 10wt% EMAA modified (a) DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44 DDS (b) TGDDM/DETDA and TGDDM/44 DDS composites cured using either the one- or two-step cure profiles after healing at T_g or above T_g.

Figure 5. SEM fracture surfaces of the 10wt% EMAA modified systems after healing at T_g for (a) DGEBA/DETDA one-step cure, (b) DGEBA/DETDA two-step cure and (c) DGEBA/44 DDS two-step cure composites. Note: TGDDM/DETDA and TGDDM/44DDS showed similar behavior to DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44DDS, respectively.

Figure 6. SEM fracture surfaces of the 10wt% EMAA modified systems after healing above T_g for (a) DGEBA/DETDA one-step cure, (b) DGEBA/DETDA two-step cure and (c) DGEBA/44 DDS two-step cure composites. Note: TGDDM/DETDA and TGDDM/44DDS showed similar behavior to DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44DDS, respectively.

Figure 7. NIR spectra of the DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44 DDS neat resin networks after a one-step cure (DETDA only) and two-step cure (DETDA and 44 DDS). Note: TGDDM/DETDA and TGDDM/44DDS showed similar behavior to DGEBA/DETDA and DGEBA/44DDS, respectively.

Figure 8. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness up to five healing cycles for the two-step cured 10wt% EMAA modified (a) DGEBA/DETDA and (b) TGDDM/DETDA composites healed below T_g , at T_g and above T_g .

Epoxy Resin	Amine Hardener	Healing Agent	Cure Profile	Abbreviation
DGEBA	DETDA	-	8 hrs 150 °C	one-step
DGEBA	DETDA	EMAA	8 hrs 150 °C	one-step
DGEBA	DETDA	EMAA	8 hrs 50 °C/8 hrs 150 °C	two-step
DGEBA	44 DDS/1.5 wt%BF ₃	-	8 hrs 150 °C	one-step
DGEBA	45 DDS/1.5 wt%BF ₃	EMAA	8 hrs 50 °C/8 hrs 150 °C	two-step
TGDDM	DETDA	-	8 hrs 177 °C	one-step
TGDDM	DETDA	EMAA	8 hrs 177 °C	one-step
TGDDM	DETDA	EMAA	8 hrs 50 °C/8 hrs 177 °C	two-step
TGDDM	44 DDS/1.5 wt%BF ₃	-	8 hrs 177 °C	one-step
TGDDM	45 DDS/1.5 wt%BF ₃	EMAA	8 hrs 50 °C/8 hrs 177 °C	two-step

Table 1 Resin compositions describing the one- and two-step cure profiles used to produce the neat resins and polymer composites.

DGEBA Resin System	TGDDM Resin System
130 °C (<T _g)	150 °C (<T _g)
150 °C (~T _g)	200 °C (~T _g)
200 °C (>T _g)	230 °C (>T _g)

Table 2. Healing temperature for mendable composites using DGEBA or TGDDM resin system

Epoxy/Amine	Modifier	DMTA (°C)	DMTA (GPa)	DSC	DSC
		T _g (ext. onset/tan δ max.)	E' at 100°C.	T _g (°C)	T _m (°C)
DGEBA/DETDA; one-step	-	150/169	1.0	158	-
DGEBA/DETDA; two-step	-	158/171	0.9	164	-
DGEBA/44 DDS; two-step	-	164/185	2.0	178	-
-	EMAA	-	-	-	85
TGDDM/DETDA; one-step	-	225/236	1.4	>200	-
TGDDM/DETDA; two-step	-	201/218	1.0	>200	-
TGDDM/44 DDS; two-step	-	222/248	1.4	>200	-
-	EMAA	-	-	-	85

Table 3. DMTA and DSC thermal analysis of the unmodified epoxy prepared and the EMMA thermoplastic used.